

Does mobility help to build bridge of collaboration between origin and destination country

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Abstract

Academic mobility is a phenomenon in today's academic landscape that facilitates global collaboration and knowledge transfer. Despite the benefits of academic mobility, concerns about brain drain persist, and fears of inequalities in mobility dynamics start to emerge. Our research explores the relationship between mobile researchers and the collaboration ties with their country of origin, revealing a remarkable trend: mobile academics maintain varying degrees of collaboration with their origin countries after moving. Scholars migrating from higher-income countries to lower-income ones exhibit a strong inclination to maintain ties with their high-income origins, but the reverse is not observed. These findings suggest unequal benefits of mobility regarding the collaboration ties, and highlight the necessity for implementing policies and initiatives geared towards nurturing more beneficial international research collaboration and harnessing the contributions of mobile scientists.

1. Introduction

International mobility among scholars has become increasingly prevalent in today's globalized academic landscape. Previous studies have explored various aspects of scholars' relocation experiences, including the motivations driving international mobility, the impact of migration on career trajectories, and the dynamics of cross-border collaboration. Additionally, scholars have investigated the role of institutional support, cultural factors, and disciplinary differences in shaping patterns of scholarly mobility and collaboration (Adams et al., 2014; Zitt et al., 2000). Scholars often emigrate to different countries for various reasons, including pursuing academic opportunities, accessing resources, and engaging in collaborative research endeavors (Fernández-Zubieta et al., 2015). Countries around the world are also actively developing policies to encourage scientists to seek knowledge abroad and the aim of promoting global scientific research exchanges.

The model of global talent flows was divided into brain drain or brain gain. Typically, benefits arise to the countries of origin of mobile scientists when these mobile researchers return,

enhancing their own human capital and social capital while on the move (Bozeman et al., 2001; Netz et al., 2020; Saxenian, 2005), and apply their acquired knowledge in academic activities back in the country of origin.

Mobility relationships facilitate knowledge exchange among scientific communities and help integrate less developed scientific systems into the global academic community (Woolley & Kjarsgaard, 2008). Returned scholars who maintain collaborative relationships with scientists in core countries or regions such as the United States and the European Union are not only cited more in international co-authored publications (Aykaç, 2021; Glänzel, 2001; Glänzel & Schubert, 2005; Leta & Chaimovich, 2002), but also bring benefits to their home country's scientific system in terms of knowledge transfer and access to international scientific collaboration networks.

Some studies suggested that mobile scholars can connect domestic scholars with foreign scholars, showing that mobile scientists create connections between their home country and the scientific system of the country where they moved (Jöns, 2009; Velema, 2012). The latest research also shows that, for instance, mobile scientists from Brazil and Colombia help increase collaborations between non-mobile scientists and foreign researchers by collaborating with non-mobile scientists (Ito et al., 2024).

This raises our interest about the extent to which academics maintain ties with their country of origin after mobility. Understanding the dynamics of scholarly collaboration ties post-mobility is essential for comprehending the evolving nature of global academic networks. Scholars' continued engagement with their origin countries can have significant implications for knowledge dissemination, cross-cultural collaboration, and the advancement of research agendas. However, the factors that influence the sustenance of such ties remain complex and multifaceted, spanning cultural, economic and institutional dimensions.

This study seeks to investigate the extent to which scholars maintain collaboration ties with their countries of origin after moving abroad to new academic environments. By examining patterns of collaboration and scholarly engagement among internationally mobile scholars, our article explores the extent of collaboration connections of mobile researchers with their country of origin, paying special attention to potential inequalities across different income level countries around the world.

2. Data collaboration & Methodology

We use bibliometrics methods to track scholars' mobility and collaboration data. The data comes from the Dimensions database, excluding publications where the author or author's country was missing, and publications with more than 100 co-authors. We then tracked publication data for all researchers who published their first publication between 1990 and 2020, and who published at least two publications. This allowed us to collect researchers across their academic careers. The final dataset contained 40,933,719 publications and 12,505,544 disambiguated authors.

We used the footprint of mobility to track researchers' affiliation changes (Dudek et al. 2022). This method tracks the mobility information of researchers between different countries year by year by determining whether there are changes in their affiliations' country. We consider a researcher to have undertaken her first mobility in her academic career when she becomes fully affiliated with a new country for the first time in a publication, and when this new country serves as the researcher's first destination (i.e. the researcher may have subsequent affiliation countries, but here we only focus on the first one).

Next, we proceeded to gather data on publications by mobile researchers in their first destination countries, identifying the affiliations of co-authors in these publications. The academic connections of mobile researchers to their origin countries are defined by the co-authored with scholars from the researcher's country of origin in publications after the researcher's first mobility. We compiled data on all emigrated scholars from their respective countries of origin and calculated the proportion of emigrated scholars that have collaboration connections with their origin country when they are in their first destination. Furthermore, we determined the proportion of immigrated scholars who moved to a particular country (which serves as their first destination) and continued to collaborate with their country of origin. To account for income disparities and regional differences across countries, we adopted the World Bank's income group classification (high-income, upper-middle-income, lower-middle-income, and low-income) (World Bank, 2020).

3. Results

To assess the extent to which mobile scientists uphold academic connections with their origin country after moving, we calculated the proportion of scholars who left and collaborated with their origin country, categorized by the role of the country in the original context (Figure. 1). The dataset encompasses a global representation, including 113 countries of origin, each with more than 100 academic scholars leaving the country. Our findings reveal differences in how mobile researchers maintain ties to their country of origin, depending on their country of origin. For instance, the proportion of mobile researchers departing from China and maintaining collaborations with their Chinese counterparts post-mobility is 51%, while the collaboration rate for scholars originating from the United States is 47%, followed by South Korea at 44%, Italy at 42%, and Germany at 41%. Notably, these collaboration rates exhibit variability across diverse countries of origin.

Overall, countries in North America exhibits the highest proportion of emigrated researchers engaged in collaboration with domestic partners (41%). Subsequently, for countries in East Asia and the Pacific, an average 28% of emigrated researchers maintain collaboration with their origin country, with standout countries including China (51%), South Korea (44%), Japan (41%), and Australia(35%). Emigrant researchers from Europe & Central Asia countries closely follow behind at 26%, with those moving from European countries showing a higher propensity to maintain ties with their countries of origin compared to counterparts from Central Asian countries. Sub-Saharan Africa, South Asia, Latin America & Caribbean, and the Middle East & North Africa exhibit the lowest levels of collaboration, each around 23%, 21%, 21% and

20%, respectively.

Figure 1: Proportion of emigrated researchers who maintained collaboration contacts with their country of origin per origin country

Figure 2: Proportion of emigrated researchers who have collaborated with their country of origin after moving across region of origin country. The red diamond indicates the mean of each boxplot. The red baseline line represents the percentage at the global level.

Having investigated the extent of academic connections maintained with the origin country by researchers migrating from the country, we further explore the extent of academic connections maintained with their origin country by researchers migrating to this country. We calculated the proportion of scientists migrating to each country who continue to collaborate with their home country and presented the results in Figure 3. The figure 3 highlights 118 countries and regions as destinations, each of which has an inflow of more than 100 scholars. China leads the way with 55% of inflows maintaining collaboration with their country of origin, followed by Grenada (55%), New Caledonia (53%), Panama (53%), and South Korea (52%). For China and

South Korea, for the two different roles of the origin country and the destination country, both outflow and inflow researchers collaborate more with the country of origin.

Figure 3: Proportion of immigrated researchers who maintained collaboration contacts with their country of origin per destination country

Fewer researchers (34%) who immigrated to Europe & Central Asia countries collaborate with their countries of origin. In comparison, 40% of researchers who immigrated to Sub-Saharan Africa countries, 41% to East Asia & Pacific countries, and 42% to Latin America & Caribbean countries were recorded as collaborating with their country of origin.

Figure 4: Proportion of immigrated researchers who have collaborated with their country of origin after moving across region of destination country. The red diamond indicates the mean of each boxplot. The red baseline line represents the percentage at the global level.

We conducted further analysis to examine the relationship between mobility flows and

collaboration with the origin country. Specifically, we examined the extent to which mobile researchers between countries with different income levels maintain collaboration ties with their country of origin. The results are summarized in Table 1.

Our results indicate that scholars migrating from higher income countries to lower income countries exhibit a higher proportion of collaboration with authors from their respective higher income origin countries. Conversely, scholars migrating from low-income countries to high-income countries demonstrate lower collaboration rates with peers from low-income countries. For instance, among individuals moving from China, classified as an upper-middle-income country, to the United States, categorized as a high-income country, 52.7% of mobile researchers collaborate with scientists from China, whereas, conversely, among those moving from the United States to China, 62.5% keep collaborating with colleagues from the United States.

		Destination country			Ave.
		High income	Upper middle income	Lower middle & Low income	
Origin country	High income	0.34	0.40	0.39	0.36
	Upper middle income	0.31	0.36	0.43	0.32
	Lower middle & Low income	0.25	0.34	0.22	0.26
	Ave.	0.32	0.39	0.39	0.34

Table 1. Proportion of mobile researchers who maintain contact with origin countries across income groups of origin and destination country

4. Discussion

The findings of this study provide valuable insights into the dynamics of scholarly mobility and collaboration, shedding light on the extent to which mobile scientists maintain ties with their countries of origin after moving to new academic environments. Our analysis reveals that a considerable proportion of researchers continue to collaborate with their home countries post-mobility, serving as bridges between their origin and destination countries and expanding international collaboration networks.

The concept of brain drain, traditionally viewed as a loss for the origin country, is nuanced by our findings. While the emigration of skilled individuals may lead to concerns about talent loss, it also fosters increased interaction between scholars from origin countries and those in high-

income countries. This enhanced contact not only facilitates knowledge transfer but also enriches the human and social capital available to scholars from the original countries.

The results highlight the importance of understanding the complex interplay between origin and destination countries, as well as income disparities, in shaping patterns of scholarly collaboration. Scholars migrating from high-income countries to low-income destinations are more likely to maintain collaboration with peers from their respective high-income origin countries. Conversely, collaboration rates with low-income countries are lower among academics migrating from low-income to high-income countries.

These findings underscore the need for more nuanced policies and initiatives aimed at fostering international research collaboration and leveraging the contributions of mobile scientists, particularly by paying attention to potential inequalities in the benefits of mobility between countries and regions. Efforts to promote cross-border collaboration and remove barriers to mobility can harness the potential of mobile researchers to drive innovation and contribute to global scientific progress.

While our study provides valuable insights, it is important to acknowledge its limitations. The analysis is based on quantitative data and may not capture all aspects of scholarly mobility and collaboration. Future research could complement these findings with qualitative approaches to gain deeper insights into the motivations and experiences of mobile scholars.

In conclusion, our study contributes to a deeper understanding of global scholarly networks and informs efforts to promote international research collaboration. By recognizing potential inequalities in mobility flows, and supporting the contributions of mobile scientists, policymakers and academic institutions can work towards harnessing the potential of international collaboration to address global challenges and advance scientific knowledge, while minimizing or reducing existing global collaboration and mobility inequalities.

Open science practices

We used the database Dimensions, which is a licensed database available at the CWTS SQL server. The scripts to process the data can be found in the GitHub of the first author [gehl0921 (github.com)].

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None

Author contributions

Huilin Ge: Conceptualization, Methodology, Data curation, Visualization, Formal Analysis, Writing – original draft. Clara Calero: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing –review& editing, Supervision. Rodrigo Costas: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing –review& editing, Supervision.

Competing interests

The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.

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